

MANAGERIAL ACTIVITIES AND COMPETENCES OF THE TUTOR.

Nurmatova Madina Odiljonovna

The Teacher Of Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11259738>

Abstract: In this article about comments about the managerial activities and competencies of a tutor are described. The article organizes the competencies specific to the leader in "Management psychology" and improves the tutor's competencies in managerial activities.

Key words: Tutor manager, competence, management competencies, tutor's leadership competencies.

Studying the laws of forming, developing, and increasing the potential of students in higher education organizations, taking into account their influence on the development of society, is always the focus of attention in the educational system. In the performance of these systematic tasks, the tutor, like the teacher, has its own unique tasks. The person of the tutor not only fulfilled the task of the main factor in creating the spiritual image of the student, but also ensured his mutual integration with the society.

The professional activity of a tutor requires a lot of knowledge and skills. A person who has realized why he chose this or that profession (the problem of motives) must now be able to manage his activities and abilities and constantly work on himself and improve his skills. A tutor is a person who acts as an educator, a leader, a consultant, but also a group leader. As a group leader, he has many tasks, and in the process of performing these tasks, he should be able to show that he is a professional person with many competencies. In the course of our research, we studied the competencies specific to the leader in "Management psychology" and tried to improve the competencies of the tutor in the management activity.

The concept of competence from this point of view requires the knowledge of technical processes and skills that ensure the improvement of skills, in addition to the knowledge that applies only to his profession, in such a direction of personal general culture. does. This means understanding the process, interpretation and passage in psychology. In the course of total scientific research, we present a description of the socio-psychological classification of competencies related to the activities of many additional production installers and professional sympathizers related to personal service managers:

- to be able to set the goal - to be able to develop appropriate tasks in educating students;

- motivational support - to strengthen students' interest in reading activities;
- education of team work skills - ability to integrate into the student team, teach the group to work together;
- equal distribution of tasks to students - giving students freedom of choice to solve difficult issues, solve controversial questions and achieve success in the way of goals;
- development of students' capabilities - feeling of responsibility, team work, helping to develop the capabilities of employees;
- attention to communication - being able to control the process of providing students with information;
- oral communication - students are able to clearly express their thoughts when working together and during a conversation;
- written communication - to be able to write ideas clearly in writings related to work;
- persuasive communication - being able to organize the delivery of information (oral or written) to convince students;
- being able to understand others - to be able to anticipate and notice students' attitudes and feelings, as well as empathically communicate their thoughts to others;
- to influence others - to be able to find people who agree and support their ideas, goals, projects and decisions
- establishing cooperation - being able to establish relations with persons involved in the education of students;
- collecting diagnostic data - knowing the information necessary to clarify the situation; searching for such information using relevant sources (the question should be asked in such a way that even a person who does not want to share the information does not know that he has answered);
- analytical thinking - ability to solve problems using logical, systematic, sequential approaches;
- prospective thinking - to find the result of the situation, the undiscovered aspects, and also to take necessary measures to be ready for a possible situation;
- explanatory thinking - being able to find an effective solution with the help of holistic, abstract and theoretical thinking;
- Competence in the field of ICT - ability to demonstrate in-depth knowledge and skills in the field of information and communication technology;
- initiative - being able to receive appropriate instructions or see what needs to be done before a strong need arises;

- to aim for the result - to pay full attention to the result expected from one's or the team's work, to set complex but achievable goals, to spend all one's energy on them, to achieve the goal and even beyond it;
- Conscientiousness - making sure that one's own work and that of others are fully completed, and that the information is verified, prepare hard for presentations and conferences, and not be indifferent to the fate of students;
- persistence - the ability to make complex decisions quickly and ensure their execution;
- self-confidence - confidence in one's own ideas and chances of success and the ability to form a system of self-analysis and correction;
- stress management - able to control oneself when pressure is applied and in conflict situations, to understand students' stress and to be able to recommend ways to get out of stress;
- to be reliable - to be able to show that one is a responsible, trustworthy person, especially to be able to keep certain information about them a secret in front of students;
- to be adaptable, flexible - adaptability to new ways of working, to be ready to modernize your favorite way of working;

A tutor should be able to find and apply effective ways of influencing his students in any situation. The degree of influence will be effective only if it is based on the use of people's inclinations and needs. Only then the tutor's commands, orders and tasks can give unexpected results

References:

1. O. Khaitov.- "Management psychology". Tashkent 2008.
2. Z.D. Khasanova.- "Management psychology". Bukhara 2021

